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TERMS AND EPONIMS OF CHILDREN'S DISEASES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK

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ABSTRACT: The article provides examples of the construction of medical eponyms in English and problems in translating them into Russian. Eponyms as part of the language of science contribute to a deeper understanding of human activity and its culture. The sublanguage of medicine is the most important source of knowledge about the people who created this science, and the current trend in modern linguistics towards the study of the human factor allows us to consider eponymous terms in the light of a cognitive approach.

Key words: medical terms, medical eponyms in English, translation of English texts.

Eponyms are words in which a proper noun is the first component. These terms play a prominent role in naming new phenomena or discoveries in the field of medicine in connection with the established international tradition to name a particular discovery or invention by the name of the scientist who made this discovery or invention. There are several names here: - diseases (Hodgkin's disease - Hodgkin's disease); - syndromes (Down's syndrome - Down's syndrome); - anatomical units of the body (Horner's muscle - Horner's muscle); - medical theories (Flecherism - Fletcherism); - research and treatment methods (Bailey's method - Bailey's method); medicines (Salk and Sabin vaccine - Salk and Sabin vaccines); - medical instruments (Cooper's scissors - Cooper's scissors); - tests for the definition of diseases (Dick test - Dick test).

The clinical syndromes and symptoms associated with the names of literary heroes of novels and stories of the 18th-20th centuries are interesting, imaginative and well remembered. Some of these characters are popular today (Pickwick's syndrome is named after one of the characters in Ch. Dickens's novel *The Pickwick Papers*; Alice in Wonderland syndrome after the heroine of the book of the same name by the English writer L. Carroll; Albatross cider is named after named after a character in *The Tale of the Old Mariner*, Samuel Taylor Koltros).

Eponyms can be divided according to the method of formation - noun + of + proper name (ampulla of Vater < Abraham Vater; pouch of Douglas < James Douglas); - proper name, transforming into an adjective (Gasserian ganglion < Johann Gasser;

Haversian canal < Clopton Havers); - proper noun + 's + noun. Based on this, we can conclude that in terms of its word-formation possibilities, medical terminological vocabulary is unlimited.

Having no equivalents in other languages, the analyzed medical terms are borrowed by different languages and become part of the international vocabulary. In addition, universal characteristics are clearly manifested in the Russian language. The widespread use of eponyms in term formation is explained, first of all, by the existing tradition, the desire to perpetuate the names of doctors and pioneer scientists who contributed to the development of medicine. Eponymic terms make up the majority of medical terminology, for example, in neurology, eponyms make up about 30% of the entire terminological fund.

More than 16% of eponymous terms are units stating the thematic group Methods of Investigation and Treatment, i.e. the names of the results of individual research and medical activities of specialists. Eponyms can be divided into the following groups:

1) name of research methods - German doctors discovered research methods, when nominating using key terms - test, reaction, method, experience: Schellong test (F.Schellong, 1891-1953, German doctor)

- functional test in the study of blood circulation, Jaffe reaction (M.Jaffe, 1841-1911, German doctor) - a method for determining creatinine in urine and blood serum;

2) anatomical terms - in the XIX century. discoveries in the field of anatomy were designated in terms by the names of German anatomists and physiologists - Gis bundle (W.His, 1831-1904), Gis angle, Ludwig ganglion (K.F.W.Ludwig, 1816-1895.), Zinn's ligament (J.G.Zinn, 1727- 1759);

3) names of diseases - the names of doctors are also found in the names of diseases, for example, the names of German doctors are imprinted in the names of diseases of the nervous system: neuropathologists and psychiatrists - Alzheimer's disease (A. Alzheimer, 1864-1915), CreutzfeldtJakob disease (H.G. Creutzfeldt, 1885-1964 , A.Jakob, 1884-1931), therapists - Reiter's disease (H.C.J. Reiter, 1881-1969);

4) the names of the symptoms of diseases - Avellis syndrome (G.Avellis, 1864-1916) - a combination of paralysis of the soft palate and vocal muscle, Berger's paresthesia (O.Berger, 1844-1885), (J.A.Barre, 1880-1967) - syn.: biceps femoris reflex;

5) names of surgical operations - based on the general terms "operation" and "plastic", eponyms were created with the names of German surgeons - Bruns operation (P.E. Bruns, 1846-1916) (fibroma removal operation), Bergmann operation (E. Bergmann, 1836-1907, the operation of excision of the own shell of the testicle); Bruns plastic lips (V. Bruns, 1823-1883, operation to restore the upper lip);

6) names of medical instruments and devices - the names of ophthalmologists in the name of tools for eye operations - Bunge spoon (P. Bunge, 1853-1926), Waldau-Graefe tweezers (A. Graefe, 1828-1870), Graefe cataract knife (A. Graefe Synonym: linear cataract knife), Graefe tweezers (A. Graefe);

7) the names of genera of bacteria formed from the names of researchers - the names of German bacteriologists are used in the name of bacteria - Klebsiella (s) (Klebsiella, Ber; E. Klebs, 1834-1913), Klebsiellosis (klebsiellosis) - an infectious disease, Koch bacillus (R. Koch, 1843-1910) - the causative agent of tuberculosis.

The translation of eponyms causes certain difficulties, which are associated primarily with the national specifics of their use in medical literature. In particular, very often the names of scientists are omitted when using medical terms or not used at all. The word "eponym" came to us from the Greek language. It consists of two parts "epi", which can be translated as "above, in addition" and "onym", which means "name".

Thus, an eponym is the name of a person, real or fictional, on the basis of which another word or phrase is created. The name of the city "Rome" can be considered an eponym on behalf of the mythical hero Romulus; Yekaterinburg - on behalf of Empress Catherine II; on behalf of Queen Victoria, the eponymous term "Victorian era" was formed, etc. In linguistics, an eponym is understood as a terminological phrase, one of the components of which is a proper name. R. Nestmann notes that the reason for the appearance of eponyms is the need to designate newly appeared phenomena. These terms play an important role in naming new phenomena or discoveries in the field of medicine in connection with the established international tradition to name a particular discovery or invention by the name of the scientist who made this discovery or invention.

Today it is difficult to find a field of medicine where eponyms are not used to one degree or another. They constitute a significant part of medical terminology, because, due to the presence of a proper name in the composition of the term, it can be the only acceptable one: synonymous terms do not always reflect the essence of the

concept, and defining a concept using a verbose descriptive construction is not convenient. For example, in English, the option is more preferable: Hoffman's reflex, and not "a reflectory reaction of muscles after electrical stimulation of sensory fibers in their innervating nerves" (flexion of the fingers in response to pinching irritation of the nail plate of the third finger of a passively hanging brush).

Based on the data studied and our own observations of the features of eponymous terms, it can be argued that all English-language eponymous terms can be divided into 5 groups, according to the method of their formation. The most common way is to add an apostrophe 's to proper names, for example, Hodgkin's disease - chronic malignant lymphomatosis. In 1832, T. Hodgkin described seven patients who had an increase in lymph nodes and spleen, general exhaustion and loss of strength. In all cases, the disease was fatal. After 23 years, S. Wilks studied in detail the cases described by Hodgkin, added 11 of his own observations to them and called this condition Hodgkin's disease.

The second most common way to form medical eponymous terms in English is to use a proper name without any changes, for example, Bell palsy - sudden weakness and paralysis of one side of the face due to trauma to the facial nerve. This eponym takes its name from the Scottish surgeon Charles Bell (1774-1842). Throughout his life, the doctor was interested in human vessels and nerves. In 1821, Bell was able to publish his book of observations, where all the symptoms of idiomatic facial paralysis were described.

The fifth group includes a few eponyms that have moved from a proper name to another part of speech. As a rule, these are verbs, for example, "to kocherise" - an operating technology for opening the duodenum with ulcers. The term was formed on behalf of Emil Theodor Kocher, a Swiss surgeon (1841-1917), who devoted his life to the study of physiology. In the English medical vocabulary, there are also abbreviated homoacronyms that are not eponyms, but graphically resemble proper names, for example: ELISA (enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay - enzyme immunosorbent test) and ADAM (androgen deficiency aging male - age-related androgen deficiency in men).

The frequency of use of these terms in the scientific community is quite high, especially if its structure consists of four or more components. As rightly noted by E.V. Varnyavskaya, the proper name is part of the cognitive layer of the term. It is a share,

a segment of the core of the concept and contributes to the generation of new meanings in the professional language picture of the world. Possessing an individualizing function, the proper name gives uniqueness to each terminological unit, which leads to the diversity of the professional language picture of the world. Despite this, some terms are criticized by experts who believe that the person whose name was immortalized in memory due to the term is not worthy of it.

The question arises about the exclusion or renaming of "inappropriate" terminological units. But even this reaction cannot affect the fact that an established and convenient term is simply forgotten. It lives its own life, functions in the scientific literature and does not go out of use. Examples of this are the following terms with the names of the neurologist Julius Hallervorden and the psychiatrist Hugo Spatz, who conducted their experiments on the brains of murdered children.

It is worth noting that the following difficulties may arise when using eponyms in scientific terminology:

- Eponyms based on the same proper name do not imply that they are referring to the same doctor, which can lead to cultural confusion, e.g. the Pick cell, Pick's disease, and Pick's pericarditis were named after (respectively) Ludwig Pick (German pathologist), Arnold Pick (Czech psychiatrist) and Friedel Pick (Austrian doctor). Eponyms based on the names of doctors from other countries can be very difficult to read and write for non-native speakers of this language, for example, Kupffer cell, Kuntscher nail, Papanicolaou smear, Hirschsprung's disease, etc.

Eponymic terms, although they are included in the dictionary corpus, they are very often not provided with any phonetic marks, that is, transcription. This greatly complicates their use in oral professional discourse.

Eponyms that mean the same concept can be formed from different proper names in different countries, for example, "Kashin's disease" and "Bek disease" are used to mean "an endemic disorder in childhood." Despite these problems, eponymous terms are an integral part of the medical terminology of different languages, which forms the scientific discourse.

Eponyms as part of the language of science contribute to a deeper understanding of human activity and its culture. The sublanguage of medicine is the most important source of knowledge about the people who created this science, and the current trend

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